

Leaf number difference between two parental lines can be used to determine the seeding interval when the leaf growth rates (leaf growth rate = number of days taken to produce the first 7 leaves divided by 7) of the parental lines are the same. For example, the leaf growth rate of CMS line IR58025A and restorer IR40750-82-2-2-3R is the same (6.4) and the leaf number difference between them is 1.3 during the DS. Therefore, for seed production of hybrid IR58025A / IR40750-82-2-2-3R during the DS, the male parent is sown first and the female parent is sown later, when the earlier sown male parent has produced 1.3 leaves.

In cases where parents differ in their leaf growth rate, the seeding interval is determined by using the following formula: seeding interval (d) = leaf number difference × leaf growth rate of the early sown parent. ■

Rice seedlings showing different leaf numbers.

Leaf number and growth duration of parental lines of promising hybrids at Hyderabad, India^a.

Parental line	Leaf number					Days to 50% flowering				
	1994 WS	1995 WS	1995 DS	Mean	CV	1994 WS	1995 WS	1995 DS	Mean	CV
IR58025A	15.7	15.3	15.0	15.3	1.83	103	98	113	104.6	6.23
IR62829A	16.2	16.0	15.9	16.0	0.81	96	89	106	100.0	7.59
Vajram	18.3	18.6	18.6	18.5	0.75	112	119	144	125.0	10.98
IR10198-66-2R	15.6	15.4	15.0	15.3	1.64	90	87	101	92.6	6.49
IR40750-82-2-2-3R	16.1	16.1	16.3	16.2	0.61	111	102	125	112.6	8.40
IR54742-22-19-3R	18.5	18.0	18.8	18.4	1.89	111	109	142	120.6	12.53
IR29723-143-3-2-1R	17.1	17.8	17.3	17.4	1.69	119	116	143	126.0	9.58

^aWS = wet season, DS = dry season, CV = coefficient of variation.

Adapting hybrid rice seed production technology

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The success of hybrid rice cultivation in India depends on a successful seed production program. Optimizing row ratio, determining the economic dose of

GA₃ and its stage of application, and identifying a suitable substitute for GA₃ are required for hybrid rice seed production.

An experimental study revealed that the row ratio of female to male of 6:1 recorded the highest hybrid seed yield of 1,921 kg ha⁻¹. GA₃ application increased plant height, panicle exertion, flag leaf angle, seed setting percentage, and seed yield. Comparatively, the proportionate increase in seed set and yield was high

when applying GA₃ at 125 g ha⁻¹. For GA₃ application, the 15-20% panicle exertion stage was found to be ideal for obtaining maximum seed set and seed yield.

Besides GA₃, applying a 2% foliar spray of juvenile leaf extract of *Albizia amara* and 2% urea spray enhanced seed yield by increasing panicle exertion and seed set in the cytoplasmic male sterile line. ■